

Cross-border database harmonisation for subsurface modelling perspectives: A case study of the Geneva Basin and neighbouring France Quaternary

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Abstract: Cross-border geological models provide a useful basis for the development of shared understanding of the underground/subsurface and thus assisting the promotion and diffusion of geological data across neighbouring nations and the management of transborder natural resources (i.e. underground water, geothermal fluids, hydrocarbons, etc.) and possible associated issues (ground water pollution and over exploitation, etc.). Effective engineering of cross-border projects, such as underground infrastructures or regional groundwater protection programs, relies on a solid and uniform geodatabase system. In the case of the Canton of Geneva in Switzerland and neighbouring France, the geological knowledge of the subsurface is inconsistent. More specifically, data type, coordinate reference system, well stratigraphy description, etc., are organised and structured in a very different database architecture. In this study, we collected, integrated, harmonised and stored geological data from the BRGM's InfoTerre subsurface database (French geological survey), into U_SOLSTISS, a Unige local version of the official SOLSTISS database (New subsurface information system of the Canton of Geneva) developed by GESDEC (Geology, Soils and Waste Department of the Canton of Geneva). This study focuses on the Quaternary strata in order to harmonise the well stratigraphy of cross-border areas, addressing the occurrence, extension and distribution of different glacial and interglacial cycles across the Geneva Basin and neighbouring France. This study, therefore, presents a homogenous and harmonised cross-border Quaternary stratigraphic scheme database that highlights the lateral and vertical characteristics of the geological units in the study area. This ultimately serves as crucial input necessary for providing an updated Model of the Base Quaternary/ Top Molasse surface, which will be used in the framework of the feasibility project for the new CERN Future Circular Collider (FCC), a new research facility tunnel located at a depth of ca. 200 m with a circumference of 90.7 km.

Keywords: Cross-border, geological model, harmonisation, Molasse, Quaternary, BRGM, SOLSTISS, FCC, CERN, Geneva, France.

Résumé : Harmonisation transfrontalière des bases de données pour les perspectives de modélisation du sous-sol : étude de cas du Quaternaire du bassin genevois et de la France voisine. - Les modèles géologiques transfrontaliers constituent une base utile pour le développement d'une compréhension commune du sous-sol, ce qui facilite la valorisation et la diffusion des données géologiques entre les pays voisins, la gestion des ressources naturelles transfrontalières (eaux souterraines, fluides géothermiques, hydrocarbures, etc.) et des éventuels problèmes associés à la pollution et surexploitation des eaux souterraines, etc. Les projets transfrontaliers tels que les infrastructures souterraines ou les programmes régionaux de protection des eaux souterraines reposent sur un système de géodatabase solide et uniforme. Dans le cas du canton de Genève en Suisse et de la France voisine, la connaissance géologique du sous-sol n'est pas homogène et présente des incohérences. Plus précisément, le type de données, le système de référence des coordonnées, la description de la stratigraphie des puits, etc. sont organisés et structurés dans une architecture de base de données très différente. Dans cette étude, nous avons collecté, intégré, harmonisé et stocké les données géologiques de la base de données InfoTerre du BRGM (Service géologique national) dans U_SOLSTISS, une version locale de la base de données SOLSTISS (nouveau système d'information territorial du sous-sol du canton de Genève) développée par le GESDEC (Service de géologie, sols et déchets du canton de Genève). Cette étude se concentre sur la géologie du Quaternaire afin d'harmoniser la stratigraphie des puits dans les régions transfrontalières. Cette étude présente donc une base de données stratigraphiques du Quaternaire transfrontalière unifiée et harmonisée qui met en évidence les caractéristiques latérales et verticales des unités géologiques dans la zone d'étude. Cette base de données est essentielle pour la mise à jour de la surface 3D de la base du Quaternaire/ top du Molasse qui sera utilisée dans le cadre du projet de faisabilité du nouveau Future Circular Collider (FCC) du CERN, un nouveau tunnel destiné à une nouvelle installation de recherche situé à une profondeur d'environ 200 m et d'une longueur de 90,7 km.

Mots-clés : Transfrontalier, modèle géologique, harmonisation, Molasse, Quaternaire, BRGM, SOLSTISS, FCC, CERN, Genève, France

1. INTRODUCTION

The development and management of a harmonised cross-border geological subsurface database across national borders are essential for the success of mutual projects encompassing groundwater management and protection, geothermal programs, infrastructures, etc. (Tulstrup & Pedersen, 2018). However, in these cross-border frameworks, there might often be issues related to subsurface data consistency, accessibility, coherence, and reliability. These challenges have to be addressed in order to harmonise and standardise a geological database that will be used for such cross-border projects. In this regard, a newly proposed cross-border project by the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) The FCC Future Circular Collider (CERN, 2023) is set to develop a major underground research facility that will involve excavating a circular tunnel nearly 90.7 km long, positioned about 200 m deep in the Canton of Geneva, as well as the French departments of Haute Savoie and Ain. This tunnel will cross the Switzerland-France border four times (Fig. 1). Several collaborators from public and private sectors are involved in this project to carry out preliminary feasibility studies. The University of Geneva in particular, has been mandated to develop an accurate 3D subsurface geological model of the Base Quaternary/ Top Molasse and Top Cretaceous in support of the engineering feasibility and tunnel design phase.

In this framework, this study aims to establish a Geographic Information System (GIS)-based subsurface dataset and database architecture in support of the feasibility of the FCC which would provide accurate data and knowledge on the nature of the subsurface geology and in particular the heterogeneity of the subsurface between the Geneva Basin and neighbouring France. This database, a repository of critical subsurface data and knowledge, will inform high-resolution 3D geological models and guide decisions on future geological analyses along the FCC trace, particularly in critical areas (i.e. Lake Geneva, river crossing, proximity to possibly active seismogenic faults, etc.), which could be required. These 3D geological models, derived from the harmonised datasets, will in turn support the design, planning, and implementation of tunnelling works along the FCC trajectory.

The presence of different stratigraphic nomenclatures across national borders complicates the construction of a homogeneous database and eventually the basis to construct a consistent geological model (Strasky et al., 2016). Therefore, in our case, the harmonisation of the stratigraphy crossing the French Swiss borders is necessary to build a homogenous model. Without this, it

is impossible to understand the lateral distributions of geological units and to create a realistic subsurface geological model.

Focusing on the area affected by the FCC project, several cross-border projects have been promoted by the national and international government agencies aiming to assess the potential of the Alpine foreland basins for the sustainable exploitation and management of natural resources such as underground water, geothermal energy, etc. (Swisstopo, 2023). Among these initiatives, two distinct projects GeoMol contributed to 3D geological modelling of the North Alpine Foreland Basin, (i) The transnational European GeoMol project (Capar et al., 2015), conducted at the scale of the entire North Alpine Molasse Basin (including the South Alpine Molasse Basin), (ii) The Swiss GeoMol project (Swisstopo, 2023), led by the Swiss Federal Office of Topography (Swisstopo), focused specifically on the Swiss sector of the North Alpine Foreland Basin and produced a national-scale 3D geological model (https://www.geomol.eu/home/index_html). This served as a basis for assessing the geothermal resources and underground storage capability (methane, CO₂) (Capar et al., 2015; Swisstopo, 2023). Also, the Geothermie 2020 program aimed at improving the understanding of the Geneva Basin subsurface and its geothermal energy potential. This program included a geological and geophysical acquisition campaign that spanned the Canton of Geneva and portions neighbouring France. Multiple 2D seismic campaigns, such as those conducted in 2018 and 2023, went beyond the immediate border and featured profiles situated entirely within French territory, yet still within the Geneva Basin (GEOthermies, 2022; SIG, 2023). In contrast, the 3D seismic campaign was geographically more limited, covering only a small area of neighbouring France. On a Swiss national scale, the Geotherm database initiative was promoted by the Swiss Confederation to support deep geothermal energy exploration projects. It provides geological, hydrogeological, and geophysical data relevant to the exploration and utilisation of geothermal resources in Switzerland (Boulicault, 2016). The GeoQuat project, promoted and piloted by Swisstopo, was initiated to develop a national Quaternary database and to produce 3D geological models aimed at characterising the spatial heterogeneity of Quaternary subsurface formations. In this context, the project carried out in the area “Praille-Acacias-Vernets” (Gaehwiler et al., 2019) as part of the GeoQuat initiative provided a general framework for understanding subsurface heterogeneity within the Geneva urban environment. However, as the pilot area was located entirely within Swiss territory.

Fig. 1. Overview map showing outcropping geological units and simplified structural elements in the study area crossed by the FCC layout, modified from BRGM (La Carte Géologique Métropolitaine à 1/1 000 000, 2003)

Finally, the HARMOS project was an initiative promoted by Swisstopo since 2011 to generate a nationwide lithostratigraphic catalogue. It ensures the homogeneity of geological maps in Switzerland (Swisstopo, 2013; Morard, 2014; Swiss Geological Society, 2016; Strasky et al., 2016; Brentini, 2018). This project aimed at establishing a standardised geological terminology by considering the existing Swiss lithostratigraphy and incorporating from neighbouring countries such as Austria, Germany, France, and Italy. The harmonisation of the Quaternary stratigraphic classification in Switzerland has been emphasised to address regional inconsistencies (Graf & Burkhalter, 2016). The results of the harmonisation of the lithostratigraphy in Switzerland are shared online (Lithostratigraphic lexicon of Switzerland Strati.ch (<https://www.strati.ch/de/>)). Other cartographic products have been generated and improved from the HARMOS project, such as the Geological Atlas of Switzerland 1:25'000 (GA25) map and the digitised format under the name of Geocover (<https://www.swisstopo.admin.ch/fr/modele-geologique-2d-geocover>).

In France, the French national geological survey, known as BRGM, started in 1998, developed the platform/database InfoTerre. This represents an institutional online platform collecting scientific and technical information with a map viewer tool, which allows for the discovery and understanding of the subsurface geology and related natural resources. InfoTerre offers easy access, search, view and download

of digital Geo-localised soil and subsurface data and other interoperable geoscientific data such as geological maps with different scales, aquifers, natural risks, etc. to assist professional planners and the general public. In 2013, the French Geological Reference project was launched, aiming at collecting and integrating geological information from the French surface and subsurface to create an information storage and classification within the BRGM information system for easy use, interpretation, synthesis and information retrieval. Data are uploaded into geological information platforms called InfoTerre and GeoField (BRGM, 2013, 2023) (<https://www.geofield.org/>). This led ultimately to the generation of new harmonised geological maps of the national territory and allowed the user to interrogate and exploit the database with a different level of sophistication.

A substantial part of the groundwater in the Geneva Canton is supplied by rivers and underground reservoirs located in the surrounding French territory (Haute Savoie and Ain) (Moscarello, 2021). Four main Quaternary aquifers have been identified in the canton, two of which, the Genevois and Allondon aquifers, are used to provide potable water (OFEV, 2024). The other two, Montfleury and Rhône, are currently being studied as part of the Geothermie 2020 programme (GEOthermies, 2022).

In the neighbouring French territories, additional aquifer systems play an important role in the regional hydrogeological context. Karstic groundwater reservoirs are developed in the Jurassic and Cretaceous limestones

of the High Jura Chain and Pays de Gex (Ain). In Haute-Savoie, several Quaternary alluvial aquifers are located along the border with Geneva, including the Genevois, Arve, and Cluse of Annecy aquifers, as well as the Bas-Chablais system, composed of the upper and lower terraces of Thonon-les-Bains, and the karst system of the Bornes Massif (ADES, 2024; BDLISA, 2024). The Genevois aquifer, which extends beneath a significant portion of the cantonal territory (Fig. 2), is primarily recharged by meltwater originating from the Arve River as well as local precipitation. Although it is jointly utilised by Swiss and French communities, particularly those located in proximity to the Salève foothills. Its subsurface architecture and cross-border extent towards the Annemasse region remain inadequately characterised due to a lack of comprehensive hydro-geophysical data (OU and DT, 2011; SAGE ARVE, 2014; DIN and DT, 2021). Swiss and French authorities jointly manage the Genevois aquifer through a long-standing transboundary agreement,

including an artificial recharge system from the Arve River. This cooperation ensures sustainable groundwater levels and supply reliability, and is internationally recognised as a model for shared aquifer governance (De los Cobos, 2018). In particular, the connection and extension of the Genevois groundwater aquifer to neighbouring France (Annemasse urban agglomeration) is still inaccurate due to the lack of detailed hydrogeological studies, including geophysical data. While the Genevois aquifer benefits from natural protection due to its coverage by thick impermeable layers, shallow groundwater bodies in the region are significantly more exposed. These vulnerable systems require strict preventive measures to ensure long-term groundwater quality and to avoid impairing natural flow dynamics (DIN & DT, 2021).

Fig. 2. Principal cross-border aquifers of Geneva canton and neighbouring France (SITG, 2023; BDLISA, 2024)

This study aims to develop a harmonised cross-border subsurface geological database (U_SOLSTISS) by integrating and standardising borehole data from the BRGM InfoTerre platform (France) into a Geneva-based geodatabase structure (SOLSTISS). The work specifically targets the Quaternary succession, a stratigraphically complex and laterally heterogeneous interval overlying the Molasse, with the goal of creating a consistent

lithostratigraphic framework across the French-Swiss border. Through a systematic methodology combining data collection, geoprocessing, reinterpretation, and harmonisation, the study addresses inconsistencies in stratigraphic nomenclature, coordinate systems, and data formats. The final unified dataset serves as the foundation for an updated 3D geological model of the Base Quaternary surface, supporting the feasibility study of

CERN's Future Circular Collider (FCC). Additionally, this work lays the groundwork for further geological analyses, including facies modelling and stratigraphic reinterpretation, focused on the Quaternary evolution of the Geneva Basin and neighbouring France.

2. DATASETS

The data set used for harmonisation in this work is represented by borehole records acquired from neighbouring France and Switzerland in the Canton of Geneva. The sources of these data are : (i) GESDEC (Catalogue | SITG (ge.ch)) and (ii) BRGM (InfoTerre Platform: <https://infoterre.brgm.fr/page/i-infoterre>).

2.1. InfoTerre open data source from BRGM

InfoTerre contains "La Banque du Sous-Sol: BSS of BRGM" (Fig. 3), which is a database that stores and manages the geological and technical descriptions of

underground structures (drillings, boreholes, underground structures or excavation work) on the French territory. This database is not relational. Hence, all the shape files are formed by flat attribute tables. To understand the BSS data structure, several classifications (labels) of boreholes, related to the availability of documents and the verification by the BRGM geological team (Table 1), have been introduced. The documents include logs, drilling reports, or just descriptions of different lithologies, geophysical logs, soil analyses, photographs, or any other type of technical documentation etc. This paper is the second in a series planned to publish the results of our study of the stratigraphy and ammonites of the Tithonian outcrops along the transect Cerro Lotena-Cerro Granito of the Neuquén Basin (Fig. 1). The ammonites of the Family Himalayitidae Spath, 1925 were the subject of the first paper of the series (Parent & Garrido, 2021).

In this paper we present the description of the ammonites of the Family Simoceratidae Spath, 1924 from our bed-by-bed collection.

Table 1. BRGM database layer classification and corresponding number of boreholes present in the study area, see Fig. 3 for spatial distribution of boreholes by layer classification

Class	Layer classification	Number of boreholes
1	With verified geology and documents	484
2	With verified geology and no documents	105
3	Without geology documents available	621
4	Initial geology with documents	1175
5	Initial geology without documents	902
6	Without geology or documents	1791
	Total Boreholes in the study area	5078

A borehole is labelled as "verified" when the associated report (information, stratigraphy, location...) has been examined, confirmed, and found to be reliable and consistent by experts, geologists or BRGM engineers. Some boreholes can be verified without formal written documentation once the experts have confirmed the information directly in the field or using other reliable methods (BRGM, 2013), which, however, are not specified in the InfoTerre documentation. A borehole is labelled as "unverified" when the verification described above is missing. This data originates from initial, unverified sources. The label "No documents" means that no information (e.g. written report, drawing, etc.) is available for this borehole. The "initial geology" label refers to a classification of data that presents initial observations and information on the geological setting of a site before any detailed analysis or verification is carried out. In this work, we focus on a selection of a borehole (in blue in Fig. 6) from the BRGM datasets (Fig. 3), which have been classified between 1 to 4 (See Table 1 and Fig. 3). In addition to the classification criteria, the selected boreholes are among the deepest and specifically include the top of the Molasse formation, which was essential for

defining the Quaternary base. Unfortunately, among the collected boreholes, the number of boreholes per classification was not recorded, as this information is not explicitly provided with each borehole in the InfoTerre database. The boreholes classified as 5 and 6 were excluded from the analysis due to insufficient geological information (See Table 1).

2.2. SOLSTISS Database architecture

The SOLSTISS (Système d'Information Territorial du Sous-Sol) serves as the present subsurface information system for the Canton of Geneva. Its database is made accessible through the website SITG platform (ge.ch, 2022) that allows for the centralisation of all data related to geological projects, whether they involve geothermal energy, soil and subsurface studies, or construction in general. The data processed by GESDEC is stored in relational geodatabases and file tree systems.

In the SOLSTISS database, data are classified and described using object catalogue tables. For each table, various data attributes (such as name, ID, type, and description) are detailed (Favre, 2018; Brentini, 2018;

ge.ch, 2022; SITG, 2023). The SOLSTISS database is accompanied by a structured metadata catalogue (in Excel sheet format), which is distinct from the database itself. This catalogue documents the content and structure of the database, detailing table schemas, field names, data types, and descriptions, thereby ensuring clarity, consistency, and traceability in data management.

For each geological project (geothermal energy, hydrogeology, geo-engineering), data are collected, centralised, and stored in SOLSTISS. The development of a data model allows the definition of the structure of the relational database through a modelling process (Fig. 4) (Favre, 2018). It also gathers all the data on geological

objects, i.e., status of borehole (producing, abandoned, equipped, etc). Another dataset, such as seismic and electric survey lines, outcrops, and geothermal installations of both open and closed system types, is not yet implemented and is planned for inclusion in upcoming development work (Favre, 2018; ge.ch, 2022). The conceptual model of SOLSTISS demonstrates how the data is stored and archived in a centralised and indexed system to ensure quick access to information for government officials, planners, and the public alike (Favre, 2018).

Fig. 3. BSS database layer classification from InfoTerre platform (Visualiseur InfoTerre, 2024)

The GESDEC manage the geological, hydrogeological, geophysical, geothermal, polluted sites, gravel pits, soil and waste (ge.ch, 2022). Therefore, data originated from diverse types of sources, mostly from prospection (i.e. boreholes, geophysics surveys) associated with geotechnical, hydrogeological, exploitation (sand and gravel pit) and recently geothermal projects. The data are entered through a web-based interface developed by GESDEC, following a quality control process. The geological information of the borehole database is used to produce maps and subsurface geological models. The SOLSTISS database allows dynamic infill with access to the latest subsurface data from projects across the Geneva

canton. The SOLSTISS also includes data inherited from an older cantonal borehole database, which contained fewer attributes. Older borehole records are being progressively reviewed and enhanced using original logs, equipment details, and status reports to meet current SOLSTISS standards.

Through the SITG platform, the public can access to borehole data (more than 20,800 boreholes as of May 2024), as well as maps displaying isolines and depth models of key Quaternary stratigraphic units, such as the Top Riss and the Base Quaternary/Top Molasse (LFM), etc. (Fig. 5) (SITG, 2023).

Fig. 4. Simplified relational model of the SOLSTISS Database (Système d’information Du Sous-Sol, ge.ch, 2022).

2.3. U_SOLSTISS database

The U_SOLSTISS presents the same database architecture and content as the SOLSTISS database, except that it also contains data from the BRGM InfoTerre. The U_SOLSTISS is stored in a local environment at the University of Geneva (hence the prefix “U_” (Fig. 6), and it represents the key database for the FCC project. The UNIGE database is disconnected from the original SOLSTISS database of GESDEC which is not populated with data from nearby French territory and collected from the BRGM database. The infill of U_SOLSTISS started in January 2022 with 19,419 boreholes. For this study, U_SOLSTISS is defined to be the environment of data storage and collection of data approved by CERN, and therefore, it is defined as the only source of data in support of the FCC project.

Fig. 5. Chronostratigraphic Column of the Geneva Basin showing the Riss and Würm complexes separated by an Eemian-Interglacial (Int), overlying the lower freshwater Molasse unit (LFM). The age framework for Quaternary stratigraphy follows Gibbard & Cohen (2019) for ages and the stratigraphic units to the SOLSTISS database (ge.ch, 2022).

Fig. 6. Boreholes from the U_SOLSTISS database include SOLSTISS boreholes (red) and BRGM boreholes (blue).

3. METHODOLOGY

The Research by UNIGE started by collecting data from the deep and shallow boreholes containing information on the Base Quaternary/Top Molasse, which represents a well-recognised surface and was recorded by boreholes in both Swiss and French territories (Fig. 5). The project also requested integrating and harmonising data (i.e., stratigraphic naming convention, etc.) from multiple subsurface boreholes stored in the InfoTerre open data source into U_SOLSTISS. The adopted workflow consisted of two tasks: (1) establish a Geodatabase using ArcGIS Pro software (2) transfer and interpret datasets on a modelling software, Petrel™ (2014).

In detail, the workflow of the first task was organised as follows: (i) bulk data collection from the BRGM is performed following verification of information within the supporting documents, (ii) Primary storage of required data into a flat ArcGIS database in the format of .Shp or Excel for geoprocessing steps, (iii) selection of the boreholes according to their depth, presence of geological units of interest, validity of information and relevance for the specific project of interest, in this case, the FCC. (iv) Infill and harmonise the data into the U_SOLSTISS database as final storage using the SOLSTISS catalogue as a guide. These steps are summarised in the workflow reported in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Workflow for harmonising borehole data from BRGM (InfoTerre) into the U_SOLSTISS system.

3.1. Geoprocessing steps

The data collection was carried out over eight months through the open database InfoTerre during two different work phases: the first from October 2020 to April 2021 to collect all the required boreholes, and the last in July 2023 for more recently drilled boreholes. The U_SOLSTISS is supplied with 842 boreholes from BRGM. At the present day, U_SOLSTISS contains exactly 20,100 Boreholes (Fig. 6).

The Collection of bulk geographic datasets from BRGM of several types is loaded and stored in a common file system folder in shapefile format and an Excel sheet. The database is created on the ArcGIS software and is intended for the management, storage, updating, infilling, and consultation of data and their different attributes. This allows for the comparison of information from the French and Swiss datasets side by side. This visual and organised setup helps quickly spot which data represents the same attributes (Total depth, groundwater level, etc.), even if they have different names. After this comparison, the harmonisation process can standardise these attributes, ensuring both datasets use the same terms. This step-by-step approach simplifies integrating and analysing the combined data.

In the verification process, 385 boreholes were found in both the SOLSTISS and BRGM databases. Most of these boreholes were drilled during the construction of the earlier CERN colliders and were originally sourced from an outdated cantonal boreholes database that lacked comprehensive geological and hydrogeological details. Out of these, 171 reached the top of the Molasse formation, yet they possess only partial or no geological and hydrogeological data in the SOLSTISS database. Currently, these records are being progressively updated by re-evaluating original borehole logs to fill in the missing attributes, ensuring alignment with the current database structure.

The geometric harmonisation of the coordinate reference system (CRS), an essential part of the geoprocessing steps, was carried out to avoid data heterogeneity (Gedrange et al., 2011). The SOLSTISS is projected in the Swiss coordinate system (Projects spatial system CH1903+ LV95). Subsequently, boreholes integrated in U_SOLSTISS database are projected using a projection tool from ArcGIS to convert the X and Y from the French system (Lambert 93 projection, (BRGM, 2013)) to the Swiss coordinate system using specific parameters and rules (CRS-EU, 2014). For boreholes with missing or incorrect coordinate values, the projection tool in ArcGIS Pro was used to accurately correct and assign their spatial position.

If elevation values were absent or incorrect, either in the U_SOLSTISS or the BRGM database, corrected values were derived from the boreholes report and manually input into the database. The elevation information could be extracted from the digital elevation model (DEM) from

two different sources: (i) “BD ALTI” from France (BD ALTI® | Géoservices (ign.fr)) with a resolution of 25 m. (ii) MNT25 from Switzerland, generated by the Swisstopo (MNT25 (admin.ch)), also with a resolution of 25 m (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Geoprocessing steps

Some deep boreholes do not encounter the Top Molasse, indicating a locally thick Quaternary succession. These boreholes are essential for better constraining the Base Quaternary / Top Molasse boundary, which is required for developing a more accurate 3D geological model along the planned FCC trajectory. Ongoing work and subsurface investigations within the FCC project aim to refine this surface. Boreholes on either side of the French-Swiss border often show inconsistent stratigraphic descriptions, highlighting the need for harmonised data to improve geological modelling.

2.3.2. Database Harmonisation

The harmonisation of borehole data into the U_SOLSTISS database required a systematic infill of attributes already defined in the initial cantonal SOLSTISS database (Favre, 2018). These consist of five attribute tables (Fig. 9) which aim to ensure consistency of the geological information associated with each borehole, regardless of its origin (i.e. France or Switzerland). The five attributes are the following:

- “GEOL_ADMIN” (object’s unique identifier) is a common table and links to all the attribute tables. This forms a central table of the database and corresponds to the ‘administration table’.
- “UNITE_GEOL” (Geological units): This table describes the different geological layers. The information is based on the documentation provided (from the borehole report).
- “GEOL_SONDAGE” (Geological borehole) is a shapefile format as a point type. It provides a technical description of the borehole survey.
- “GEOL_QUAT”: this table describes in detail the lithology of the Quaternary units. The “classification des sols genevois” was developed by GADZ for the Geneva Quaternary successions (Deriaz, S.A & Ruchat, 1997). Local authorities and stakeholders use this geomechanical classification for subsurface characterisation and engineering applications.
- “GEOL_HYDROGEOLOGY”: This table describes the hydrogeological units. It contains the piezometer, depth of the aquifer, and geological units of the reservoir.

Fig. 9. Attribute Tables from the SOLSTISS database. The connections enable efficient linking and sharing of data across tables (Data extracted from the SOLSTISS database and modified using ArcGIS Pro)

Table 2. Description of the Quaternary geological units from the SOLSTISS database catalogue (Translation from the original French version of the SOLSTISS catalogue)

Period	Age	Geological unit	Code SOLSTISS
Quaternary	Holocene	Terrains de couverture/cover soil	1-2
		Colluvions ; Terre végétale/colluvial and vegetal soils	1
		Remblais hétérogènes / backfill	2
		Ruissellements ; Colluvions/ Runoff; Colluvium	3
		Dépôts palustres/ Palustrine deposits	3
		Alluvions récentes/ Recent alluvium	4
		Alluvions indifférenciées/ Undifferentiated alluvium	4-9
		Dépôts lacustres/ Lacustrine deposits	5
	Tourbe/ Peat	5	
	Pleistocene	Retrait glaciaire indifférencié/ Undifferentiated glacial withdrawal	6-11
		Retrait würmien / Würmian withdrawal	6
		Moraine indifférenciée/ Undifferentiated moraine	7-12
		Moraine würmienne/ Würmian moraine	7
		Dépôts intra morainiques/ Intra moraine deposits	8
		Alluvion ancienne/ Ancient alluvium	9
		Interglaciaire Riss-Würm/ Interglacial Riss-Würm	10
		Retrait rissien/ Rissian withdrawal	11
		Moraine rissienne/ Rissian moraine	12
		Dépôts intra morainiques/ Intra-formational deposits	13
		Non renseigné /Unknown	N/A
Autre/ Other		N/A	

All these attribute tables are related to the Geological borehole through the admin ID from the GEOL_ADMIN attribute table. Therefore, all these attributes' tables adopt "Geol" as a prefix.

The integration of data from the borehole into these attribute tables is a manual process. Each borehole is filled individually by adding all information from the borehole reports and logs. The data infill is controlled and well guided by the domain already set up in SOLSTISS and detailed in the catalogue. Any other description not included in the catalogue is not considered and is deleted by the system.

The stratigraphy encountered in the boreholes ranges from the base of the Jurassic to the Holocene. All the names of geological units are established by GESDEC based on the local geology of the Canton of Geneva and

are applied to the UNITE_GEOL attribute table of SOLSTISS (Table 2). Many geologists have studied the Quaternary deposits in the Geneva Basin and neighbouring France, starting with Necker (1841) and Favre (1878, 1879). Favre was the first to compile borehole data in his geological description of the Canton of Geneva. Later, Penck and Brückner (1909) proposed an early glacial stratigraphy for the region. Subsequent work by Joukowsky (1920, 1927) and Paréjas (1938), and Jayet (1946) further described the stratigraphic variability of the Quaternary successions (Fig. 5). The stratigraphic units are systematically coded based on the SOLSTISS database conventions, with full documentation provided in the associated documentation within the SOLSTISS catalogue (Table 2).

The BRGM database presents differences in the nomenclature of Quaternary geological units, and in some boreholes, this information is missing because the geological descriptions focus more on lithology than on stratigraphic units. This inconsistency between the Swiss and French datasets, especially in lithological descriptions, poses a key challenge for harmonisation and complicates automated correlation.

To address this, lithological descriptions have been systematically reinterpreted to distinguish geological units and enable data harmonisation. Where Quaternary units were not identified or remained unclear, they were classified as 'unidentified'. This approach was applied to several boreholes that, despite lacking direct Quaternary data, encountered the Base Quaternary/Top Molasse boundary.

Using lithological and stratigraphic information from the SOLSTISS database, it has been possible to harmonise the geological units across datasets (Fig. 10).

The Fig. 10 outlines a simplified workflow for harmonising BRGM borehole data using lithological descriptions and the SOLSTISS stratigraphic framework. Lithological descriptions from BRGM boreholes are reinterpreted using the GADZ (1965) classification criteria. These units are then standardised to the SOLSTISS framework using the SOLSTISS catalogue to ensure consistency in the geological framework of this database (Table 2). The harmonisation is validated by correlating with adjacent boreholes, where available, to confirm stratigraphic coherence (Fig. 5). However, in the French records, both the Riss complex and the interglacial interval are not present in the BRGM nomenclature and may be absent or unidentifiable. In some cases, these units can be identified using neighbouring boreholes.

Similarly, individual advances within glacial cycles such as Riss or Würm are not documented (Fig. 5); typically, only a single advance is described. This contrasts with the geological understanding of the Geneva Basin, where multiple advances are expected based on stratigraphic and geomorphological evidence (Moscarillo, 1996). Due to these limitations, classification of Quaternary units in

French boreholes relied on thematic interpretation of lithological descriptions, aligned with the stratigraphic framework applied by GESDEC.

In some instances, boreholes contain both lithological and stratigraphic descriptions, facilitating direct correlation

with adjacent records. These cases simplify the harmonisation process by providing internal stratigraphic anchors that enhance consistency across the regional geological framework.

Borehole source InfoTerre

FICHE TECHNIQUE			
Nom du Chantier : Villa Win - Veigy Foncenex			
Forages N° : 1 à 4			
Travaux exécutés du 10 au 14 décembre 2007			
Tubage Ø 152 mm.	de m. 00.00	à m. 10.00	Remarques
			4 sondes de 80 m
Destructif Ø 130 mm.	de m. 00.00	à m. 80.00	
COUPE SOMMAIRE DU TERRAIN			
00.00 - 02.00 m.	Remblai, terre végétale	10.00 - 80.00 m.	Molasse
02.00 - 06.00 m.	Moraine		
06.00 - 10.00 m.	Argile, molasse		
Venues d'eau	de m. 46.00	à m. 50.00	Débit estimé 20 - 40 L/min.
Remplissage avec matériel de forage			
Travaux supplémentaires			
Rallonge des sondes : 2 x 18 et 2 x 12 m			
Test des sondes et des rallonges.			

Analyse the geology description of the borehole key surface in this case Base Quaternary / Top Molasse

Depth	Litology
0-2 m	terre végétale
2-6 m	moraine
6-10 m	Argile Molasse
10-80 m	Molasse

Reinterpretation and harmonisation of the geology of the borehole based on SOLSTISS frame work

Depth	Litology	Harmonised stratigraphy	Stratigraphy	Code SOLSTISS
0-2 m	terre végétale	cover soil	Holocene	1-2
2-6 m	moraine	Würmian moraine	Pleistocene	7
6-10 m	Argile Molasse	Würmian moraine	Pleistocene	7
10-80 m	Molasse	Molasse indifferencited	Pleistocene	14-15

Confirm the geological description and classification of geological unit using neighbouring borehole

Borehole source SOLSTISS

Visualization of correlation with neighbouring borehole using Petrel software

Fig. 10. simplified workflow of borehole (ID: BSS001QCJR) harmonisation from the InfoTerre open data source into the U_SOLSTISS framework. This figure illustrates the harmonisation phase within the overall workflow for integrating BRGM data into U_SOLSTISS in Fig. 7

3.3. Data transfer

The data transfer is the process of securely moving information from one system to another. In our case study, data were transferred from the U_SOLSTISS database to a software enabling 3D subsurface modelling, such as Petrel (SLB, 2024), used in this project. The required raw geological data from U_SOLSTISS were thus transferred into usable information with the selected software, which allowed data visualisation, analysis and modelling. This transferred dataset included the harmonised boreholes from the BRGM database alongside the existing boreholes from SOLSTISS. All boreholes were assigned the same “ID_Sondage” number from U_SOLSTISS, which is the identifier in modelling software to facilitate the verification of raw data from the borehole report. The selection of the boreholes to be exported from the U_SOLSTISS into the modelling software was based on:

(i) the data quality of the logs /reports, for boreholes inherited from the SOLSTISS database, was checked prior to their integration into the modelling software, (ii) the presence of the Top Molasse and (iii) their distribution in the study area. The data transfer procedures allow a second opportunity to control the accuracy and reliability of data during the integration of geological data, such as borehole location and geological unit description, and therefore avoid a possible negative impact on the geological model. Thus, many boreholes have been revised for stratigraphic inconsistency with the neighbouring ones to ensure alignment between borehole data. These may help to identify unnoticed errors during the database input of the U_SOLSTISS. The transferred dataset included location (X, Y), elevation depth (Z) calibrated with the DEM, facies and geological units and borehole total depth (TD) (see Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. Data transfer from database to modelling software (SLB), visualisation and valorisation (Borehole correlation and surface generation)

A simple lithofacies description was then established to characterise the geological units of the UNITE_GEOL attribute table from U_SOLSTISS into Petrel (see Table 3). This simplification was necessary due to the high number of lithological and stratigraphic distinctions in the SOLSTISS database (Table 2), which are detailed for direct application in facies modelling workflows. To address this, lithological units with similar textural, sedimentological, or depositional characteristics were grouped into lithofacies categories. This approach allows for constructing a more coherent and manageable facies model while retaining the geological integrity of the original data. Simplifying the facies classification reduces complexity in the dataset, which stabilises spatial

interpolation algorithms and ensures the geological model aligns more reliably with established regional geological patterns.

Table 3. Lithofacies associated to Quaternary units in Petrel Model and codes within the U_SOLSTISS database.

Period	Geological units	Lithofacies Petrel	Code U_SOLSTISS
Holocene	Postglacial	Soil	1-2/1/2
		Peat	5
		Fluvial	4/4-9
		Lacustrine	3/5
Pleistocene	Würm withdrawal	Glaciolacustrine	6-11/6
		Gravity mud/debris flow	6-11/6
		Glaciofluvial	6-11/6
	Würm Glaciation	Till/moraine	7-12/7
		Inta-glacier	8
		Till	7-12/7
	Interglacial	Fluvial	10
	Riss withdrawal	Glaciolacustrine	11
		Gravity mud/debris flow	11
		Glaciofluvial	11
	Riss Glaciation	Till/moraine	12

4. U_SOLSTISS HARMONISATION UTILITIES

4.1. Data Processing

The data harmonisation was essential to ensure coherence and cross-border homogeneity of the geological model, with the focus on the Quaternary stratigraphy of the last glacial period. Despite the utilisation of the classical description of the geological units of the Quaternary succession, the SOLSTISS presents a better classification and description than neighbouring France. Several projects have been carried out in Switzerland towards data harmonisation, including the definition of methodologies, standards, and guideline protocols (Strasky et al., 2016). On the other hand, this was not done systematically for the boreholes present in the BRGM database. Therefore, the quality control of the BRGM database, including data validation, cleaning, standardisation and integration of collected boreholes, is an essential and necessary step. The harmonisation of the Quaternary succession in the study area was therefore a challenging and time-consuming part of the data processing.

4.2. Stratigraphic interpretation and Surface generation

The stratigraphic interpretation derived from the harmonised boreholes forms the basis for generating continuous surfaces of the Quaternary succession. These data contribute to reinforcing the geological model of the FCC and will also be used in future work to construct a sedimentary facies model (ongoing work) representing the spatial distribution of Quaternary deposits in the

Geneva Basin. The facies model, to be developed based on the harmonised borehole data using the SOLSTISS stratigraphic framework, will allow for a reassessment of the stratigraphic architecture of Quaternary units and support reservoir characterisation of unconsolidated Quaternary sequences using geological modelling.

The borehole data allow the generation of geological surfaces and thus contribute to understanding the geological setting of the study area. These surfaces were generated for Quaternary successions from interpolated elevation values of various Quaternary unit tops. Data points (stratigraphic tops) were interpolated, and gridding algorithms were applied using mapping software such as Petrel™ (2014).

The limited number of boreholes in the cross-border area often constrains the quality of interpolation and reduces the accuracy of the surface generated with borehole data (Fig. 6).

In areas where 2D or 3D seismic data are available, the stratigraphic interpretation of boreholes and their correlation can be guided by the interpretation of seismic lines. This can enable the stratigraphic relationships between layers, seismic facies and key geological surfaces and geometries, such as glacial incisions and their infill, which may not be captured by boreholes. Therefore, the interpretation of the seismic lines can improve the quality of the final stratigraphic interpretation and surfaces derived from it. Aspects related to the integration of seismic and borehole data across time and depth domains are not addressed in this chapter.

4.3. Facies model

A harmonised data set characterised by consistent stratigraphic and lithological classifications can be used effectively for generating a facies model. This can be used to highlight the complexity and heterogeneity of the Quaternary deposits during the glacial and interglacial periods and the occurrence of potential reservoirs and groundwater aquifers. In the Geneva Basin, the facies model is a key to understanding the evolution of the basin during the geological history. Previous models, such as the GeoQuat facies model (Gaehwiler et al., 2019), were geographically limited, restricting their use in broader, cross-border geological interpretations. In contrast, the harmonised dataset developed in this study provides the basis for a more extensive facies model that will extend into the cross-border region, including parts of neighbouring France. The unified dataset established in this study substantially extends this scope, offering a more comprehensive regional facies model that integrates data from both Swiss and French territories.

4.4. Database QC

Data quality control determines whether or not the data is reliable. Consequently, it is imperative to verify the quality and suitability of data before utilisation and

effective decision-making. Thus, the quality check during the data collection from BRGM was needed to improve the 3D geological model. Therefore, for each data collection phase the following tasks were carried out: i) check and add –unavailable coordinate system and Elevation depth, ii) check the quality of existing information to identify data completeness and consistency, iii) evaluate the report before filling-in information of the geological units (Top Molasse, Top Cretaceous); (iv) ensure stratigraphic accuracy by comparing borehole data from neighbouring ones.

Most of the examples where inconsistent data were encountered in both SOLSTISS and BRGM databases were caused by misinterpreted stratigraphic units, data entry errors and incorrect borehole location (geographical coordinates and altitude of boreholes that did not match with the elevation model of the region). For example, when boreholes are poorly reported, with missing files, or unclear, corrupted, or erroneous reports from the BRGM database, a correction is carried out prior to importing into the U_SOLSTISS database. During the geoprocessing step, some boreholes were revealed to have incorrect X and Y coordinate projections or were located in the same location but with different ID. If the stratigraphic description was identical in both boreholes, one of them was digitised in the U_SOLSTISS database. In most of cases, the elevation values of borehole top surfaces did not match the DEM of the region. Therefore, the borehole elevation values were modified and aligned with the DEM elevation values. These issues might potentially contribute to incomplete data and gaps within the database. In case of great uncertainty about a borehole, the latter was not integrated into the database.

The data harmonisation can be very challenging when considering the genetic and stratigraphic interpretation of a certain lithology. In the Canton of Geneva, stratigraphic nomenclature, i.e., Würm, Riss, Interglacial, etc, has been based on the lithology, generating much ambiguity about the stratigraphic unit and chronostratigraphic position. Within the BRGM database, most boreholes have only the lithological description, leaving the chronostratigraphic interpretation unresolved. Therefore, the data examined were often inconsistent and presenting incompatible information leading to uncertainties and unreliable stratigraphic subdivisions, for example, the “Riss or Würm withdraw” and “Alluvion ancienne” present the same lithology descriptions (Fig. 5, i.e. sand and gravel) but have completely different geotechnical characteristics such as the compactness, colour and density of the sediments.

5. CURRENT ISSUES AND AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT

5.1. Aquifers

Other issues in the data QC process have arisen when considering the French aquifers. Their extension and naming refer mainly to geographical location, the nature of the geological formations and the hydrological characteristics. This approach is remarkably similar to the Swiss naming criteria. However, the aquifers in the cross-border area (“Genevois” and “Rhone” aquifers) present different names, and the current SOLSTISS database does not allow a full harmonisation of the hydrogeological data set between Switzerland and France. The “Genevois” aquifer doesn't have an official status in the French aquifer classification, while it is in reality connected to the Arve aquifer in France (Fig. 2). The rest of the aquifers located far from the border have been assigned a value of “unknown” within the U_SOLSTISS.

5.2. Key parameters to be included

In the context of drilling, the measurements while drilling MWD parameters include rock mechanical properties, porosity, and pore pressure. This is extremely useful information as it is able to determine the nature of the rocks, such as lithology, compactness and therefore help predict the crossed stratigraphic units. From a geological perspective, geologists can identify the lithology and possibly the formations being drilled using this measurement parameter. The variations in drilling parameter values may indicate changes in formation hardness, lithology transitions, or the presence of geological structures such as faults or fractures (Lee & Lee, 2023; SLB Energy Glossary, 2024). Although not typical in standard Quaternary drilling practice, this emphasises the possible advantage of incorporating such data to improve subsurface interpretation and aligns with the larger goal of enhancing the quality of borehole documentation.

These data are routinely collected while the drill bit passes through the rock, but almost never recorded in the database. Among these properties are the optimal drilling control parameters WOB, RPM and analytical ROP model.

WOB: weight-on-bit (lbs), refers to the downward force exerted on the drill bit by the drill string and the weight of the entire drilling assembly (SLB Energy Glossary, 2024).

RPM: Rotation Per Minute of the drill string (revolutions/sec), is the rotational speed (SLB Energy Glossary, 2024). It is a standard unit of measurement used in drilling operations to indicate the speed at which the drill string rotates while drilling into the subsurface.

ROP or Rate Of Penetration (ROP). ROP (ft/hr) or (m/hr), depends on the measurement system used.

It is influenced by factors such as rock hardness, drilling fluid properties, weight on bit, rotary speed, and bit design (Lee & Lee, 2023). The change of ROP values is an indication of formations encountered while drilling. For example, a sudden increase in ROP may indicate the transition from softer to harder formations, while decreases in ROP may signify the presence of shale or other low-resistance formations (SLB Energy Glossary, 2024). ROP is a function of RPM and WOB (Hegde et al., 2019).

Gamma ray (GR) logging measures the natural radioactivity of subsurface materials and is commonly used to characterise lithological variations along a borehole. In Quaternary sequences, it is particularly effective in identifying fine-grained sediments such as clays, which typically exhibit higher radioactivity than sands or gravels. Gamma ray data can support the interpretation of lithological boundaries and stratigraphic transitions, especially when integrated with lithological logs. Its ability to provide continuous, non-destructive records makes it highly recommended for improving borehole characterisation and supporting stratigraphic correlation.

As indicated above, the collection of these data and the quantification of the drilling parameters for specific lithology (i.e. compacted till, cemented vs unconsolidated gravel, sandy aquifer, etc.) can be used to guide geologists to perform the stratigraphic interpretation.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The harmonisation of geological data improves the quality and accessibility of subsurface information. This paper describes the steps and methodology involved in database harmonisation for cross-border projects. The database of U_SOLSTISS is one of the key deliverables for FCC CERN to carry out further studies in the area. Following this work, CERN is planning to drill more boreholes all along the future FCC trajectory to improve the knowledge of the subsurface in critical areas and thus update the geological model of the FCC. The ultimate goal is to use these borehole data to develop an accurate subsurface 3D geological model. As far as the database infill is concerned, vigilance and data control are required during data input in the database, integration and data transfer.

During the drilling and interpretation of well logs, contractors should include an examination of at least 2 to 4 wells in a 50-100 m buffer zone around the newly drilled borehole in order to ensure reliable data interpretation. Based on the observations from this study, it is recommended to adopt standardised litho- and chronostratigraphic charts, such as the SOLSTISS framework, to ensure consistent description of geological

sections in all boreholes, whether cored or drilled destructively. In addition, the results highlight the need to reconsider the historical classification of Penck and Brückner (1909) in the Geneva Basin. Future work should aim to refine the stratigraphic interpretation through targeted dating to establish a revised, locally adapted stratigraphic column for the region.

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